

Optimizing Combustion Chamber Design for Enhanced Performance and Reduced Emissions Using CFD Analysis

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Received: Jun 10, 2025

Accepted: July 04, 2025

Published: July 07, 2025

Abstract

With increasing global awareness of climate change driven by harmful gas emissions, the automobile industry is experiencing a strong push toward innovative solution. As vehicle usage continues to rise, research into improving engine efficiency and reducing emissions is expanding rapidly. This project focuses on how combustion chamber design and the distribution of the air-fuel mixture influence engine performance, efficiency, and emissions. The study investigates various combustion chamber geometries and air-fuel mixture characteristics, aiming to identify configurations that minimize emissions and enhance efficiency. Using Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) simulations, we evaluate the performance of different chamber designs in a cost- and time-effective manner. The research adopts a systematic trial-and-error approach to compare key parameters across multiple configurations. Ultimately, the objective is to determine the most effective combustion chamber design for optimal engine performance. The findings from this study are expected to contribute valuable insights to the field of automotive engineering and support the development of cleaner, more efficient vehicles.

Keyword: Combustion Chamber, Diesel engine, Design, Geometry, CFD tool, Emission, Performance

1. Introduction

Combustion refers to a chemical reaction between fuel and oxygen, resulting in the production of heat and light. This process is essential for energy generation in internal combustion (IC) engines, where the heat released from combustion drives the engine's mechanical components to generate power. The combustion chamber is the enclosed space where this controlled reaction occurs, typically located above the piston in the cylinder head of engines like those in cars, gas turbines, or rocket systems [1]. The design of the combustion chamber plays a critical role in optimizing the fuel-burning process, improving efficiency, and controlling emissions.

Internal combustion (IC) engines can be classified based on several key parameters. By fuel type, engines are categorized as diesel engines or petrol (gasoline) engines. Based on the operating cycle, they can be grouped into Otto cycle engines, diesel cycle engines, or dual cycle engines. The number of strokes defines engines as two-stroke or four-stroke. Regarding the number of cylinders, IC engines can be single-cylinder or multi-cylinder, including configurations such as twin, three, four, six, eight, twelve, and sixteen cylinders. The ignition system distinguishes between spark ignition (SI) engines and compression ignition (CI) engines. In terms of the lubrication system, engines can be dry sump or wet sump lubricated [2]. Cooling mechanisms further classify engines into air-cooled or water-cooled systems.

The valve arrangement can vary, including L-head, I-head, T-head, and F-head engines. Cylinder positioning offers further distinctions, such as horizontal, vertical, radial, opposed piston, opposed cylinder, V, W, or inline engines. Based on air intake pressure, engines are classified as naturally aspirated, supercharged, turbocharged, or crankcase compressed [3]. Finally, application-based classifications include automotive engines, aircraft engines, locomotive engines, marine engines, and stationary engines.

CI engines feature various types of combustion chambers, each with distinct characteristics that impact performance and efficiency. The open combustion chamber injects fuel directly, offering simplicity and high mechanical efficiency, but requiring higher injection pressure for atomization. The pre-combustion chamber uses a smaller pre-chamber where combustion begins before the mixture is forced into the main chamber, supporting multi-fuel engines but with lower efficiency than direct injection. The turbulent combustion chamber enhances fuel-air mixing with high-velocity air, facilitating higher speeds but with reduced mechanical efficiency due to heat losses [4]

The M-combustion chamber, developed in 1954, reduces combustion noise by injecting fuel tangentially into a spherical cavity, providing smooth operation and multi-fuel capability, though it may need assistance for cold starts. Finally, the air-cell combustion chamber uses air cells to improve mixing and power output, but suffers from higher fuel consumption and poor cold-start performance. Each design offers specific trade-offs in terms of power, efficiency, and fuel compatibility.

Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) refers to the use of applied mathematics, physics, and computational software to simulate how fluids (liquids and gases) flow and interact with surfaces. While the term "fluid dynamics" is commonly used, CFD actually encompasses a broader scope of computational transport phenomena, including heat transfer, mass transfer, and other processes involving the movement of energy or substances [5]. At its core, CFD relies on the Navier-Stokes equations, which describe the relationship between velocity, pressure, temperature, and density in a moving fluid. Initially developed in the early 20th century, CFD has found widespread applications in fields such as automotive and aerospace engineering, where it is used to analyse airflow around cars and aircraft [6].

In recent years, CFD has also become an essential tool for optimizing cooling systems in data centres. By creating a 3D mathematical model of the data centre's layout, CFD software can simulate airflow and thermal dynamics under various conditions. This allows administrators to identify hot spots, minimize wasted cold air, and make informed decisions on optimizing the cooling infrastructure. For example, if an administrator plans to rearrange racks or IT equipment, a CFD simulation can predict how such changes will impact airflow and temperature distribution, enabling adjustments to be made before any physical modifications are implemented. This proactive approach saves both time and resources while improving the overall efficiency of the cooling systems [7].

CFD has a vast range of applications across various engineering fields, reflecting its importance in understanding and optimizing fluid dynamics in complex systems. In aerospace engineering, CFD is used for both interior and exterior design—internally, it aids in air conditioning and ventilation systems, while externally, it helps shape the aerofoil sections to enhance aerodynamics. In the automobile industry, CFD assists in analysing fluid flow behaviour inside vehicles, optimizing combustion chamber designs, and estimating external drag forces [8]. Within chemical industries, CFD is used to model processes like steam injection, mixing of chemical streams, and bubble formation at interfaces. In electronics, it supports the development of efficient cooling strategies by simulating fluid flow and heat transfer around devices. For energy applications, CFD is crucial in studying emission characteristics from coal-fired boilers. In materials processing and manufacturing, it simulates grain growth in materials. Lastly, in turbo-machinery design, CFD is employed to optimize blade designs and improve flow passages through impellers and blades, enhancing overall machine efficiency.

II MODELLING AND ASSEMBLY

This process follows a trial-and-error approach, where we designed six different configurations by modifying the piston geometry and cylinder head. The configurations include two types of cylinder heads—flat and cone-shaped—and three piston geometries—flat, concave, and vortex. These variations were analysed in a virtual environment [9]. To begin the analysis, we first needed to create a basic software model. For this purpose, the components were modelled using PTC Creo 2.0. At the initial stage, we designed the following components:

Cylinder Design

Figure 1 Flat Head Cylinder

Figure 2 Cone Head Cylinder

Figure 3 Flat Piston

Figure 4 Concave Piston

Figure 5 Vortex Piston

III ANALYTIC CALCULATION

3.1 Technical specification:

TABLE 1
TECHNICAL SPECIFICATION OF ENGINE

TECHNICAL SPECIFICATION OF ENGINE		
No. of Cylinders		1
Bore x Stroke	(mm)	80 X 110
Cubic Capacity	(Ltr)	0.553
Compression Ratio		16.5: 1
Rated Output as per IS: 11170	kW(hp)	3.7(5)
Rated Speed	rpm	1500
Torque at full load (Crankshaft drive)	kN-m(kgm)	0.024 (2.387)
Crankshaft Center Height	(mm)	203
Specific Fuel Consumption (SFC)	(gm/hp-hr)	185 +5%
Lub Oil Consumption		0.8 % of SFC
Lub Oil Sump Capacity	(Ltr)	3.7 at higher level mark on
Fuel Tank Capacity	(Ltr)	6.5

Overall Dimensions of standard engine (Length x Width x Height)	(mm)	617 x 504 x 843
Engine Weight (dry) with all fittings	(kg)	130
Rotation while looking at the flywheel		Clockwise
Power Take-off		Flywheel end.
Starting		Hand Start
Governing		Class"A2/B1"
Type of fuel injection		Direct Injection
Overloading capacity of engine		10% of the rated output

According to specification,

$$B.P. = 3.7 \text{ KW}$$

$$RPM = 1500 \text{ rpm}$$

$$SFC = 195 \text{ g/KWh}$$

$$L * D = 110 * 80 \text{ mm}$$

$$(CN)_{\text{fuel}} = 43800 \text{ KJ/Kg}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 P_{bm} &= \frac{B.P * 60000}{\pi L D n} \\
 &= \frac{3.7 * 60000}{0.110 * 3.14 / 4 * (0.080)^2 * 1500/2 * 1} \\
 &= 535339.35 \text{ N/m}^2 \\
 &= 5.3533 \text{ bar}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Let, } P_{\text{max}} = 9 \text{ or } 10 P_{\text{mean}}$$

$$= 10 * P_{\text{mean}}$$

$$= 10 * 5.3533$$

$$= 53.533 \text{ bar}$$

Design of cylinder and cylinder head

- Wall thickness,

$$t = \frac{P_{\max} * D + C1}{2\sigma_{\text{all}}} \quad (\text{let, } \sigma_{\text{all}} = 45 \text{ N/mm}^2 \text{ for C.I.)}$$

$$= \frac{5.3533 * 80 + 2.3}{2 * 45}$$

$$= 7.05 \text{ mm}$$

$$= 8 \text{ mm}$$

- Thickness of flange (t_f):

$$t_f = 1.3 * t$$

$$= 1.3 * 8$$

$$= 10.4 \text{ mm}$$

$$= 11 \text{ mm}$$

- Thickness of cylinder head (t_h):

$$t_h = D \sqrt{\frac{P_{\max} * C}{\sigma_{\text{all}}}}$$

(let, material is same for cylinder head)

$$= 80 \sqrt{\frac{5.3533 * 0.1}{45}}$$

$$= 8.72 \text{ mm} = 9 \text{ mm}$$

- Dia. Of studs & no. of studs:

(Made from nickel steel)

$$d_c = D \sqrt{\frac{P_{\max}}{z * F t}}; \quad \left(\frac{D}{100} + 4\right) < N < \left(\frac{D}{50} + 4\right)$$

$$\left(\frac{80}{100} + 4\right) < N < \left(\frac{80}{50} + 4\right)$$

$$4.8 < N < 5.6$$

$$N = 5$$

$$= 80 \sqrt{\frac{5.35}{5 * 50}}$$

$$d_c = 12 \text{ mm}$$

$$d_b = \text{nominal diameter of stud} = \frac{d_c}{0.8}$$

$$= 16 \text{ mm}$$

Minimum $d_b \geq 16 \text{ mm}$

- Pitch circle diameter of stud and flange diameter

$$\begin{aligned} \circ D_p &= D + 3 d_b \\ &= 80 + 3 (16) \end{aligned}$$

$$D_p = 128 \text{ mm}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \circ D_o &= D_p + 2 \cdot d_b + 12 \\ &= 128 + 2 \cdot 16 + 12 \end{aligned}$$

$$D_o = 172 \text{ mm}$$

- Cross check of d_b :

$$19 \cdot \sqrt{db} \leq P_{bo} \leq 28.5 \cdot \sqrt{db}$$

$$\text{where } P_{bo} = \frac{\pi D_p N}{5}$$

$$19 \cdot \sqrt{16} \leq 80.42 \leq 28.5 \cdot \sqrt{16}$$

$$= \frac{3.14 + 128}{5}$$

$$= 80.42$$

Hence, d_b is safe and right for design.

Design of piston:

Here, $L/D = 110/80 = 1.375 < 1.5$, crown is provided.

$$\text{Radius of crown} = 0.7 \cdot D = 0.7 \cdot 80 = 56 \text{ mm} = R_c$$

- Piston head thickness:

$$\circ t_{ph} = 0.433 \cdot D \cdot \sqrt{\frac{P_{max}}{\sigma_{all}}}$$

$$= 0.433 \cdot 80 \cdot \sqrt{\frac{5.35}{35}}$$

$$= 13.54 \text{ mm}$$

$$t_{ph} = 14 \text{ mm}$$

Take maximum value, $t_{ph} = 14 \text{ mm}$

Ribs: - as $t_{ph} > 6 \text{ mm}$, reinforcing ribs are required.

Thickness of ribs = $t_{ph}/3$ to $t_{ph}/2$

$$= 80 * \frac{\sqrt{3*0.0535}}{100}$$

F_t = allowable bending stress

$$= 3.2049 \text{ mm}$$

$$= 84 \text{ to } 112 \text{ N/mm}^2$$

$$= 3.2 \text{ mm}$$

$$= 100 \text{ N/mm}^2 \text{ (C.I)}$$

○ Axial width = $b_r = (0.75 \text{ to } 1) * t_r$

$$= 2.4 \text{ to } 3.2$$

$$= 2.8 \text{ mm}$$

$$\text{C/S of the ring} = 3.2 * 2.8$$

○ Minimum axial width requires $= \frac{D}{100 * z}$

○ Width of top land = $(1 \text{ to } 1.2) * t_{ph}$

$$= (1 \text{ to } 1.2) * 14$$

$$= 14 \text{ to } 16.8$$

$$0.002 * 80 \text{ to } 0.004 * 80$$

$$= 0.16 \text{ to } 0.32$$

$$= 0.16 \text{ mm}$$

○ Width of other ring land = $(0.75 \text{ to } 1) * b_r$

$$= (0.75 \text{ to } 1) * 2.8$$

$$= 2.1 \text{ to } 2.8$$

$$= 2.5 \text{ mm}$$

○ Gap between free ring = $(3.5 \text{ to } 4) * t_r$

$$= (3.5 \text{ to } 4) * 3.2$$

$$= 11.2 \text{ to } 12.8$$

$$= 12.4 \text{ mm}$$

○ Gap between ring in cylinder = $0.002 * D \text{ to } 0.004 * D$

$$= 0.002 * 80 \text{ to } 0.004 * 80$$

$$= 0.16 \text{ to } 0.32$$

$$= 0.16 \text{ mm}$$

(3). Piston barrel:

$$\text{Thickness of barrel, } t_1 = b + 0.03 \cdot D + 4.5$$

(Depth of ring groove, 0.4mm larger than tr)

$$= (3.2 + 0.4) + 0.03 \cdot 80 + 4.5$$

$$= 10.5 \text{ mm}$$

At the open end, the wall thickness is,

$$t_2 = 0.25 t_1 \text{ to } 0.35 t_1$$

$$= (0.25 \text{ to } 0.35) \cdot 10.5$$

$$= 2.625 \text{ to } 3.675$$

$$t_2 = 3 \text{ mm}$$

Skirt length:

$$R_n = l \cdot D \cdot p_b \quad ; \quad R_n = (0.03 \text{ to } 0.10) \cdot F_{gmax}$$

$$= 0.1 \cdot F_{gmax}$$

$$= 0.1 \cdot \pi/4 \cdot D^2 \cdot P_{max}$$

$$= 0.1 \cdot 3.14/4 \cdot 80^2 \cdot 5.353$$

$$= 2.6907 \text{ kN}$$

$$2.6907 \cdot 10^3 = l \cdot 80 \cdot 0.45$$

$$l = 74.74 \text{ mm}$$

$l = 75 \text{ mm}$, skirt length

Assume that $P_b = \text{bearing pressure} = 0.45 \text{ MPa}$

- Piston length = $l + \text{ring section} + \text{top land}$

$$= 75 + [(4 \cdot b_r) + (3 \cdot b_o)] + b_1$$

$$= 75 + [(4 \cdot 2.8) + (3 \cdot 2.5)] + 16$$

$$= 109.7 \text{ mm} = 110 \text{ mm}$$

Piston pin : (made from alloy steel)

where, l_1 length of piston = $0.45 \cdot D$

$$l_1 \cdot d \cdot P_b = \frac{\pi}{4} \cdot D^2 \cdot P_{\max}$$

Diameter of pin = d

$$(0.45 \cdot 80) \cdot d \cdot 25 = \frac{3.14}{4} \cdot (80)^2 \cdot 5.353 \quad \text{bearing pressure } P_b = 25 \text{ MPa}$$

$$d = 29.89 \text{ mm}$$

$$d = 30 \text{ mm}$$

If pin is hollow, $d_o = d = 30 \text{ mm}$

$$d_i = 0.6 d_o = 0.6 \cdot 30 = 18 \text{ mm}$$

- Check condition :-

For shear,

$$F_{g\max} = 2 \left[\frac{\pi}{4} (d_o^2 - d_i^2) \right] \tau$$

$$26.907 \cdot 103 = 2 \left[\frac{3.14}{4} (30^2 - 18^2) \right] \tau$$

$$\tau = 29.73 \text{ N/mm}^2 < 80 \text{ N/mm}^2 \text{ (Alloy steel)}$$

For bending,

$$\sigma_{bp} = 116.2 < 150 \text{ N/mm}^2$$

Hence design is completely safe.

Finally, all the engine component part files were assembled, creating a total of six assemblies. Each assembly was modified to form cavities according to the fuel flow path. Valves were also added to introduce obstacles in the flow, simulating real-world conditions. The completed assembly represents the configuration with a flat head and flat piston as shown below.

Figure 6 Assembly of Engine

IV ANALYSIS IN ANSYS

ANSYS is a general-purpose finite element modeling package for numerically solving a wide variety of mechanical problems. These problems include: static/dynamic structural analysis (both linear and non-linear), heat transfer and fluid problems, as well as acoustic and electro-magnetic problems.

Here, we have imported the geometry, made in PTC Creo 2.0, in ANSYS 18.0. This the first to solve the any problem in ANSYS. The meshing is the next step after importation of geometry. We develop default mesh to get result so quickly. Developed mesh is shown below with result table taken during analysis.

Figure 7 Meshing and Physics Report

2. Mesh Report

Table 2. Mesh Information for CFX 5

Domain	Nodes	Elements
Default Domain	48270	236503

3. Physics Report

Table 3. Domain Physics for CFX 5

Domain - Default Domain	
Type	Fluid
Location	B119
<i>Materials</i>	
Air at 25 C	
Fluid Definition	Material Library
Morphology	Continuous Fluid
<i>Settings</i>	
Buoyancy Model	Non Buoyant
Domain Motion	Stationary
Reference Pressure	5.0000e+01 [bar]
Heat Transfer Model	Isothermal
Fluid Temperature	9.8000e+02 [K]
Turbulence Model	k epsilon
Turbulent Wall Functions	Scalable

In the set-up phase, we have to define boundary condition to get the result in our desire domain. We have bounded in reference pressure of 50 bar with average fluid temperature at point of combustion 980 K. Moreover, the inlet velocity is defined as 50 km/hr. From

the above data total 48270 Nodes are generated which is the boon of coarse mesh. All to gather around 236503 elements is solved by CFX and we get robust result.

We are judging for Turbulence Kinetic Energy (TKE) and Velocity Streamline. To reach the practical result we also bound the condition of Turbulence Intensity to the maximum level of 10%. Which count the possible all loss and give the more satisfactory result. After setting up, analysis is started. We get total six result as illustrated below:

Fig.8 Flow Analysis and TKE of Flat Head Cylinder and Flat Piston

Fig.9 Flow Analysis and TKE of Flat Head Cylinder and Concave Piston

Fig. 10 Flow Analysis and TKE of Flat Head Cylinder and Vortex Piston

Fig. 11 Flow Analysis and TKE of Cone Head Cylinder and Vortex Piston

Fig.12 Flow Analysis and TKE of Cone Head Cylinder and Concave Piston

Fig. 13 Flow Analysis and TKE of Cone Head Cylinder and Vortex Piston

V.RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the CFD tool, we analyse the results of Turbulent Kinetic Energy (TKE) and Velocity Streamlines for both geometries. TKE represents the mean kinetic energy per unit mass associated with eddies in turbulent flow and is typically characterized by root-mean-square (RMS) velocity fluctuations. This parameter is linked to the quality of the fuel-air mixture—the higher the TKE, the better the mixing. However, the final evaluation is more strongly influenced by the velocity flow, which guides us toward accurate conclusions.

The mean values of both variables help determine which geometry is more effective. The table below summarizes the key findings of the analysis.

Table 4
Comparison of variable

Parameter→ Geometry↓	Mean Turbulence Kinetic Energy (m^2s^{-2})	Mean Velocity Streamline (ms^{-1})
Flat Head Cylinder, Flat piston	6.52	31.8
Flat Head Cylinder, Concave piston	8.032	34.45
Flat Head Cylinder, Vortex piston	103.3	120.8
Cone Head Cylinder, Flat piston	9.1	31.8
Cone Head Cylinder, Concave piston	8.1	31.1
Cone Head Cylinder, Vortex piston	11.3	31.3

Based on the above values, the flat head cylinder shows improved performance when the piston geometry is modified. Among the configurations analyzed, the Flat Head Cylinder with a Vortex Piston stands out as the most effective. It delivers distinct and high values in the results. However, when a cone head is introduced, the performance trend changes—primarily due to the increased volume at Top Dead Center, which leads to a drop in pressure. In conclusion, the Flat Head Cylinder combined with a Vortex Piston geometry proves to be the most suitable option for implementation.

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE

Overall, the Flat Head Cylinder with Vortex Piston geometry demonstrates the most promising results. When this configuration is modified to a Cone Head, the performance parameters tend to decline. Therefore, the Flat Head Cylinder combined with a Vortex Piston is recommended for implementation.

As part of future work, this concept can be further explored using a combustion module, which would provide insights into soot formation, exhaust emissions, and other combustion-related characteristics. Additionally, a physical prototype will be developed to validate the simulation data. For practical applications, this concept has the potential to be implemented in real-world engines, contributing to improved performance, smoother operation, and reduced energy losses and emissions.

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